

THE INFLUENCE OF NON-TRADITIONAL DRAWING TECHNIQUES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY OF PRESCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN

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Abstract

In the article, a theoretical substantiation of the creativity development problem of older preschool children by means of non-traditional drawing is carried out. The authors consider creativity as a pedagogical category and its specifics in older preschool children and determine the features of using non-traditional drawing techniques for the development of creativity of older preschool children through giving a concise description of the most effective of them.

Keywords: creativity, development, non-traditional drawing techniques, older preschool children.

Introduction. Today, in all progressive countries of the world, the issue of developing a creative personality capable of self-realization and intellectual and creative activity is becoming more and more relevant. Reforming the educational system of Ukraine objectively determines the need for the development of individual creativity, timely identification and creation of favourable conditions for the manifestation of creative abilities of children and youth. This is fully confirmed in the Laws of Ukraine “On Education”, “On Preschool Education”, which emphasize that the revival of Ukrainian society, its progressive development largely depends on the creativity and initiative of every Ukrainian. In this regard, one of the tasks of implementing a personally oriented model in preschool education institutions is the formation of creativity in a child of older preschool age in accordance with his age capabilities.

At preschool age, every child discovers the unfamiliar and amazing surrounding world with joy and surprise, assuming the role of an explorer. Today, it is a proven fact that the comprehensive development of a child of older preschool age is more successful if he is included in various types of activities, where his potential opportunities and first manifestations of creativity are realized. As a rule, the manifestation of creativity involves the implementation of a certain activity, as a result of which a new, original product is created. That is why one of the effective and accessible types of activity in the Preschool Education Institution is artistic and productive activity. Its implementation creates conditions for the involvement of preschool children in the development of creativity, in the process of which something beautiful and original is created.

Main text. The creativity of older preschool children is manifested in any type of activity, especially in visual arts. Accordingly, the role of art in the aesthetic education of the personality is sufficiently covered in

the works of B. Brylin, V. Klymenko, I. Klymuk, L. Poberezhnoi, L. Yakovenko, N. Folomeyeva, O. Mykhailichenka, Ti. Skoryk et al. The works of B. Nikitin, J. Smith, L. Carroll, I. Belaya, and O. Kocherga are devoted to the development of artistic and creative abilities of preschool children. And although researchers comprehensively reveal the raised problem, touching on the issues of the psycho-physiological basis of human creative potential (O. Kocherga), the philosophy of creativity (J. Smith, L. Carroli), foreign experience in the development of children's creative abilities (I. Bila), we can talk about insufficient its coverage from the side of the possibilities of non-traditional drawing tools. So, we can say that one of the current directions of scientific research is the study of artistic means of developing the creativity of children of high school age.

To determine the essence of the concept of creativity, one should also analyse related concepts, such as “creativity”, “creative abilities”, “giftedness”, “perception”. Because in the psychological and pedagogical literature, creativity is most often associated with the concept of creativity and is considered as a personal characteristic.

The vast majority of scientists define creativity through personality properties, abilities that reflect the deep nature of individuals to create original values, to make non-standard decisions. Many scientists refer to this concept in connection with the concept of modern approaches to education, which emphasize the development of creativity, the ability to go beyond the known, make non-standard decisions, and create products characterized by novelty.

Psychologists R. Burns, O. Bondar, O. Dubasenyuk, S. Kramarenko and others are considering creativity as a general creative ability. They prove that creativity is connected with the development of imagination, fantasy, generation of hypotheses.

Among the prerequisites and grounds characteristic for the manifestation of creativity, scientists single out perceptual features of a creative personality, namely: intense attention, great vulnerability, without bias of perception.

Scientists include intuition, powerful imagination, fiction, the gift of foresight, and breadth of knowledge as intellectual manifestations. Among the characteristic features are evasion from the template, originality, initiative, tenacity, high self-organization, increased efficiency, etc.

As mentioned above, creativity is often replaced by inventing the new in modern research. Therefore, it is appropriate to address the essence of this concept within the scope of this study. L. Vygotsky [2], addressing creativity, points out the need to manifest and develop the ability to create something new. In his scientific works, N. Kotelyanets [8] notes that a person who has an internal plan of action is capable of full-fledged creative activity. This allows her to integrate existing knowledge from various fields of activity.

Based on the above research, creativity, as well as the ability to it, expressed by the concept of creativity, continuously develops. Development is carried out together with the development of personality and intelligence. In this regard, preschool age is the most favourable for the development of creativity.

So, within the scope of this study, we can define the concept of "creativity" as a certain characteristic of a person, which indicates his ability to be creative.

This statement is also supported by a number of researchers (L. Vygotsky, J. Gilford, P. Torrens, etc.), who define creativity as an ability or quality of an individual [2, 3, etc.].

In accordance with the above statements, P. Torrens [8] notes that the perception of shortcomings, gaps in knowledge, sensitivity to disharmony can be expressed in creativity as certain limits of the individual. The author believes that a creative person is distinguished by the presence of awareness of the problem, the search for many solutions to test the hypothesis, and the finding of a reference point that leads to a result.

On the other hand, J. Piaget and S. Pazyenko, who pay attention to the development of intelligence as a quality of creativity, implement the defined concept [11]. Representatives of Gestalt psychology M. Wertheimer, U. Koehler and others were engaged in the study of productive creative components of intelligence. There are three approaches to the study of intelligence and creativity. Let's consider each of them in more detail.

Instead, A. Maslow [9] believes that the main role in creative expression is played by motivation, values, and personal traits. They consider cognitive giftedness, sensitivity to problems, and independence of judgment in difficult situations to be the main features of creativity.

It will be appropriate to cite the opinion of O. Dubaseniuk [7], who considers the originality of children's performance of creative tasks to be the main criteria for the manifestation of creativity of older preschool children; using images of some objects to build details of others.

So, summarizing what has been said, we can conclude that such individual and psychological features of the personality as abilities, inclinations, and talents influence the development of the personality and its achievements. Preschool is a period of upbringing, development, and learning that affects the process of personality formation. This is most clearly manifested in creative activity, which allows older preschool children to fully reveal their inner world. In our understanding from the standpoint of a personal approach, creativity is a self-developing phenomenon.

It would be appropriate to note that it is in the preschool age that the basic characteristics are laid down, which will further determine the creative direction of the individual. As the most important difference in the personality of a child of older preschool age, his ability to react emotionally to the surrounding world is considered: objects, phenomena and works of art, etc. An older preschool child discovers the world as joyful, beautiful, filled with colourful colours.

Scientists have proven that personality development is influenced by such cognitive processes as acceptance and imagination. Let's consider them in more detail.

The older preschool children emotionally perceive works of art (paintings, sculptures, illustrations, decorative products, etc.), gradually understanding their artistic "language".

It is appropriate to note that the leading cognitive process of preschool age is perception. It performs a function that combines the properties of objects and their images, cognitive processes of joint coordinated work on reinterpreting information from the outside. Under the influence of various perceptual activities, children of older preschool age actively develop throughout the preschool period.

In preschool age, perception prepares thinking, gives it material for analysis, comparison, generalization, and conclusions. The thinking of older preschool children, in turn, has a positive effect on the development and improvement of perception, increasing its purposefulness and productivity.

Preschool childhood becomes a turning point in the development of attention. During this period, children first begin to consciously direct their attention, directing and holding it on certain objects. For this purpose, an ordinary older preschool child uses certain algorithms of actions, which he perceives from an adult. One of the main achievements of a typical pre-schooler is the development of voluntary memorization. This is largely facilitated by game activity, in which the ability to remember and reproduce the necessary information in time leads to success.

According to S. Humenyuk [5], an artistic and creative attitude to the subject is valuable for the development of older preschool children, which involves a number of cognitive moments. That allows older preschool children to form the ability to correlate form and content, an artistic image and the depicted object, a skill that can arise only at a certain stage of the child's development.

Speaking about the development of creativity of older preschool children, L. Shelestova [15] points out

that a child can derive great pleasure from bright colours and a variety of shapes of objects, but these are only sensory qualities of things. The author considers it important that in the process of development, children of older preschool age begin to understand that a picture is a picture, and a fairy tale is a fairy tale. After awareness, something else begins to form in the child, a special attitude to works of art, the ability to distinguish their difference from ordinary objects. The scientist further points out that such awareness is a complex process, at first the child does not notice, does not get the correct interpretation, but gradually creativity begins to manifest itself.

High emotionality, sensitivity to sensory properties is actually another characteristic feature of creativity of older preschool children. Having determined the role of perception in the development of creativity, we will further consider the features of imagination. The ability to imagine is not given from birth.

The researchers' data allow us to establish that the visual object and bright is perceived, firstly, as beautiful, arouses the child's interest, he feels joy and satisfaction when interacting with it.

Imagination develops as practical experience is accumulated, knowledge is acquired, and all mental functions are improved.

According to a number of researchers, N. Horoshchko, L. Dabyzha, a child of preschool age, is consciously an artist. "Sharpness of sight", "Freshness of perception", "Impartiality", "Brightness of impression", these are the characteristics characteristic of children's nature, which determine the aesthetic attitude of a pre-schooler primarily as a high emotional sensitivity to sensory characteristics in reality [4,6].

It would be appropriate to cite the opinion of T. Ponimansky [12], who notes that a fairly large number of older preschool children are able to demonstrate the development of creativity in activities. This is expressed in vivid imagination, visual memory and fantasy, coordinated movements, etc. But it should be borne in mind that during the development of creativity, it is necessary to form not only a faithful eye, but also skilful hands, and emotional sensitivity of the child.

Taking into account all of the above, we can determine that the development of creativity of older preschool children as individual features, qualities of an individual that determine the success of his performance of various creative activities.

Scientists call different terms for the age from which children's creativity should be developed – from one and a half to five years. There is also an opinion that it is necessary to develop creativity from an early age in all types of activities and, firstly, in games. Great potential for the development of children's creativity lies in visual arts. This is due to the fact that it is at this time that the mental processes of older preschool children improve, namely, attention, memory, perception, imagination, and others, and personal qualities are actively developed, and based on them, abilities and inclinations.

Pedagogical practice proves that intervention in the process of a child's intellectual and creative development is due to the fact that not every child is able to show creative activity on his own. The effectiveness and efficiency of nurturing the creativity of older preschool children depends on the purposefulness of this process [1, 2 etc.].

In turn, the child's abilities are formed with the help of mastering, in the process of learning, the content of material and spiritual culture, technology, science, and arts.

Only in the effective contact of older preschool children with the surrounding world, in the process of gradually mastering the achievements of the previous historical development of mankind, general and special predispositions turn into various more advanced abilities, including and creativity.

Modern pedagogical research is based on the need to study the personal development of a child in close interaction with an adult. Therefore, the relationship between educators and children, as participants in the everyday educational process, is becoming more and more interesting.

Modern pre-schoolers consider natural objects and phenomena to be the most attractive. It seems obvious that the child gets creative pleasure by connecting the imagination (it is easy to see in a plant, in a doll a spiritual being, with a special mood and character). Note that a toy never remains for a child just a thing, a close object, it becomes a symbol of children's dreams and fantasies. At the same time, children of older preschool age are attentive to the external characteristics of an object, a phenomenon, relying on them makes it possible to create images. Pre-schoolers tend to bring this or that object to life, endow it with familiar character traits, actions, and adventures. It is valuable that older preschool children are ready to fantasize about many things: about pencils, and about fallen leaves, about blooming buds, and about toys, clothes.

The inclusion of older preschool children in the types of activities available to them contributes to the accelerated development of creativity. But if this activity is not organized appropriately and is not aimed specifically at the development of creativity, then the process will be formed spontaneously. And the child will also have gaps in his ideas about a number of properties of objects and phenomena.

Emotional reactions to works of art in preschool age are characterized mainly by the experience of immediate satisfaction or dissatisfaction. In this regard, the own activities of older preschool children such as drawing, sculpting, singing, dramatization should occupy one of the central places in the development of creativity.

Raising children's creativity is also related to the development of their personality: independence, enthusiasm and independence.

The development of creativity of older preschool children has several stages: from the superficial, purely external grasp of outlines and qualities that catch the eye, to reaching the essence and depth of artistic content. Only in the older preschool age, when impressions have already been accumulated, some life experience

appears, the ability to observe, analyse, classify, compare, the child can appreciate the art object, see the difference between reality and its image.

The development of creativity in children of older preschool age occurs in the process of education and training, researchers include the most important pedagogical processes and conditions for the development of creativity: the relationship between educators and children of older preschool age, as participants in the everyday educational process; the game as a mandatory component of personal development, material means of learning (toys, objects and natural phenomena); educational environment; inclusion of the child in the types of activities available to him [13].

Thus, older preschool age is a favourable period for the development of creativity. It is at this time that progressive changes occur in many areas, mental processes (attention, memory, perception, thinking, language, imagination) are improved, personal qualities are actively developed, and on their basis, abilities and inclinations. According to the logic of the research, we will consider the peculiarities of using non-traditional drawing techniques for the development of creativity of older preschool children.

Her creative abilities have a huge impact on the development of older preschool children. General development opportunities are part of creativity, that is, the higher the level of abilities, the more prospects open up for children of older preschool age in their creativity. The samples created at the same time have more or less expressiveness, depending on the general degree of creativity development and acquired skills.

At the same time, older preschool children not only reflect what they see and feel, but also get acquainted with phenomena and objects that differ in their properties and qualities.

At first, pre-schoolers acquire the simplest drawing skills – the traditional method. And later, they look for new ways of reflecting the surrounding reality in their artistic work. This is the time when the teacher should introduce children to non-traditional drawing techniques. Such a non-standard solution develops children's imagination, removes negative emotions, allows revealing and enrich their creative abilities, which is the basis of creativity. Non-traditional drawing is a means of mental, emotional, aesthetic and volitional development of older preschool children. In the process of this activity, all mental functions are improved: visual perception, memory, mental operations. And the development of fine motor skills of the hand develops thinking and speech. The hand knows, and the brain records sensations and perceptions, combining them into images and representations [10].

Children love to draw from an early age. This type of activity fascinates and pleases them. Due to its accessibility, clarity, and concreteness of expression, it is close to the game.

The created image, in particular a picture, can perform different functions (cognitive, aesthetic), because it is created with different purposes. It should be noted that the purpose of drawing necessarily affects the nature of its execution. It has been noticed that all children like to draw when they are good at it. Drawing with

pencils and a brush requires a high level of mastery of drawing techniques, developed skills and knowledge, methods of work. The lack of this knowledge and skills quickly turns the child away from drawing, because as a result of his efforts, the drawing turns out to be incorrect, it does not correspond to the child's desire to get an image close to his idea or the real object. The beginning of work is beautiful and diverse materials – this is what helps to prevent monotony and boredom in creative activity, ensures the immediacy of children's perception and activity [4].

It is important that the teacher creates a new situation so that, on the one hand, children can apply previously learned activities, skills, and abilities, and on the other hand, they look for new solutions and creative approaches. This is what causes positive emotions, joyful surprise, desire to work and create in older preschool children.

Let's consider the specifics of traditional and non-traditional drawing in preschool age. First, the child learns such concepts as "vertical" and "horizontal", hence the linearity of early children's drawings. Even then, they grasp the forms of materials, gradually make sense of their surroundings. Moreover, this happens, as a rule, faster than the accumulation of words and associations. In this regard, drawing gives an opportunity to express in a figurative form what children of older preschool age have already learned about and what they can express verbally. Drawing in general helps the child to organize knowledge that is rapidly being absorbed.

It is necessary to understand and take into account the connection between drawing and the thinking of older preschool children. When drawing, visual, motor, and muscular sensory analysers are included in the work. In addition, drawing develops children's intellectual abilities, memory, attention, fine motor skills, teaches the child to think and analyse, compare, generalize, compose and imagine.

Researchers emphasize the fact that drawing should bring only positive emotions to children. Positive emotions comprise the basis of mental health and emotional well-being of older preschool children.

As noted by L. Dabizh [6], the child's interest in artistic creativity should be supported and developed. It is not necessary to put a pencil or a brush in an inept child's hand and torture him. The first failures will cause disappointment and even irritation in the child. It is necessary to ensure that the child's activities are successful – and strengthen his own strength.

In connection with this, it became necessary to apply such artistic techniques in the educational process of a preschool institution that could be mastered by all children and would bring maximum emotional satisfaction. Since emotions are a process, and the result of practical activity is artistic creativity.

Today, there are many techniques and drawing techniques with which you can create original works, even without having any artistic skills. Drawing with unusual materials and original techniques allows children to feel unforgettable positive emotions, that is, to learn non-traditional drawing techniques.

Practitioners emphasize that drawing using non-traditional image techniques does not tire older preschool children, they maintain high activity and work capacity throughout the time allotted for the task. In addition, non-traditional techniques allow an individual approach to children, taking into account their wishes and interests.

Their use contributes to: intellectual development of the child; development of self-confidence; development of spatial thinking; free expression of one's thoughts; development of fine motor skills of hands; freedom of choice of materials and techniques [10, 14, etc.].

The experience of using such techniques shows that the success of the development of children's artistic creativity depends on their diversity and variability. All these types of activities do not tolerate a template, stereotyping. The novelty of the equipment of the environment, the unusual beginning of work, beautiful and diverse materials, interesting and unique tasks for older preschool children. As well as the possibility of choosing many other factors — all this ensures painting and the immediacy of children's perception, helps to prevent diversity and boredom in children's creative activities.

To master non-traditional drawing methods, a wide range of different materials available to older preschool children is provided: paper of different texture, shape, and size; gouache and watercolour paints; brush No. 2,3,5; bristle brushes; wax and coloured chalk; markers, felt-tip pens; simple and coloured pencils, etc. [10].

You can and should start drawing using non-traditional techniques—according to the principle “from simple to complex”.

The main techniques used at this age: drawing with fingers, palms; cotton buds; printing with leaves, potatoes, carrots; drawing with a candle, charcoal.

The older pre-schoolers can also use such non-traditional techniques as: drawing with a candle; blotography with a tube of juice; sprinkling; imprint; drawing with foam rubber; finger painting etc.

It is worth noting that the success of teaching non-traditional techniques largely depends on the qualifications of the teacher. In order to convey to older preschool children, the content of work on each technique, it is necessary to use the most diverse methods and techniques.

Each of the above techniques is a small game. In accordance with the research objectives, we will consider each of the techniques in more detail. A more detailed description of these techniques can be found in the works of N. Horoshko, L. Dzhabil, O. Dubaseniuk, I. Lykov, N. Sarkisov, M. Stas, and others. Specialists single out the most effective techniques of non-traditional drawing with art materials for each age [4, 6, 7, 10, 13, 14 etc.]. Let's consider each of them from the point of view of opportunities for the development of creativity of older preschool children.

For any age, you can use the technique “Stick with a semi-dry brush”. Means of expressiveness in this technique are: texture of painting, colour. The materials used for this are: stiff brush, gouache, paper, any colour

and format, or a cut silhouette of a furry or spiky animal (hedgehog, cat, Christmas tree) and others. The method of obtaining the image: the child lowers the brush into the gouache and hits the paper with it, holding the hand vertically. Do not dip the brush into the water while working. Thus, the entire sheet, outline, or template is filled.

The result is an imitation of the texture of a fluffy or prickly surface. For children from two years old, you can use the “Finger Drawing” and “Palm Drawing” techniques. In the “Finger Painting” technique, the means of expression are: spots, dots, short lines, colour. With children, you can use such different materials as gouache bowls, thick coloured paper of any colour, small sheets, napkins. The method of obtaining the image: the child dips his finger into the gouache and puts dots and specks on the paper. On each finger, the child collects paints of a different colour. After work, the fingers are wiped with a napkin, and then the gouache is easily washed off with water.

In the “Palm Drawing” technique, the means of expression are: spot, colour, fantastic silhouette. The materials used for this will be needed: wide saucers with gouache, a brush, thick multicoloured paper of different colours, large-format sheets, napkins. The method of obtaining the image: the child lowers his palm into gouache (the entire brush) or paints it with a brush already at the older preschool age (from five years old) and makes an impression on paper. They draw with the right and left hands, painted with different colours of paint. After work, the hands are wiped with a napkin, then the gouache is washed off with water.

With children from three years old, you can use the technique “Print with cork”, “Print with potato stamps”. Means of expressiveness in the “Cork print” technique are stain, texture, and colour. The following materials are used: a bowl or a plastic box with a stamp pad made of thin foam impregnated with gouache, thick paper of any colour and size, stamps made of corks. The method of obtaining the image: the child presses the stopper to the stamp pad with paint and makes an impression on the paper. To get a different colour that you like, change the bowl and plug.

The technique “Potato stamps” uses such means of expressiveness as stain, texture, colour. Materials that can be used: a bowl or a plastic box, in which a stamp pad made of thin foam soaked in gouache, thick paper of any colour and size, potato stamps is inserted. The method of obtaining the image: the child presses a stamp pad with paint to his hands and makes an impression on the paper. To obtain a different colour, the bowl, and seal are changed. With children from the age of four, you can work with the techniques “Foam print”, “Splash”, “Styfoam print”, “Rubber stamp print”, “Crumpled paper print”, “Wax chalk and watercolour”, “Candle and watercolour” [10].

Means of expressiveness in the “Foam print” technique is stain, texture, colour. Materials used: a bowl or a plastic box with a stamped pillow made of thin foam, impregnated foam, gouache, thick paper of any colour and size, pieces of foam. The method of obtaining the image: the child presses the foam to the stamp with

paint and makes an impression on the paper. Other bowls and foam are used to change any colour.

When using the "Foam print" technique, the means of expression become: stain, texture, colour. Such materials are used as a bowl or a plastic box, in which a stamp is placed, a pillow made of thin foam impregnated with gouache, thick paper of any colour and size, pieces of foam. The method of obtaining the image: the child presses the foam to the stamp pad with paint and makes an impression on the paper. To get any other colour, the bowl and the foam are changed [14].

When using the techniques "Print with rubber stamps" and "Print with crumpled paper", means of expression stand out: stain, texture, colour. The following materials are used for this technique "Printing with rubber stamps": a bowl or a plastic box in which a stamp pad made of thin foam impregnated with gouache is placed, thick paper of any colour and size, then rubber stamps (the teacher can make them himself, cutting through the pattern on the rubber band with a knife or razor blade). The method of obtaining the image: the child presses the stamp to the stamp pad with paint and makes an impression on the paper. To change a different colour, you need to take a different bowl and seal.

For the "Print with crumpled paper" technique, the materials are: a saucer or a plastic box, in which a stamp pad made of thin foam impregnated with gouache, thick paper of any colour and size, crumpled paper is inserted. The method of obtaining the image: the child presses crumpled paper to a stamp pad with paint, and makes a print on the paper. To get a different colour, change the saucer and crumpled paper. For such techniques "Wax chalk and watercolour" and "Candle and watercolour" means of expression become: colour, line, stain, texture [14].

In the "Wax crayon and watercolour" technique, materials are used: wax crayons, thick white paper, watercolour, brushes. How to get the image: a child with wax chalk on white paper. Then he paints over the sheet with watercolour in one or more colours as desired. The chalk drawing remains unpainted.

The following materials are used in the "Candle and watercolour" technique: a candle, thick paper, watercolour and a brush. The method of obtaining the image: the child draws with a "candle" on paper. Then he paints the sheet with watercolours in one colour or several colours. The image of the candle remains white.

With children from five years old (that is, with older pre-schoolers), you can work with the techniques of "Stencil printing", "Subject monotype", "Ordinary blotography", "Blotography with a tube", "Blotography with thread", "Spraying", "Prints of leaves", "Watercolour chalk", "Stick".

In the "Stencil printing" technique, the means of expression are: spot, texture, colour. Let's consider them in more detail. Materials used for this: a bowl or a plastic box, in which a stamp pad made of thin foam impregnated with gouache is placed, thick paper of different colours, a foam pad, a ball of fabric or foam is placed in the middle of the square and the corners of the square are tied with a thread, then stencils from oiled semi-cardboard or transparent film. The method of obtaining the image: the child presses the print or a foam

pad to a stamp pad with paint of any colour and makes an impression on paper using a stencil. To change the colour, another swab or stencil is taken.

Means of expressiveness in the technique "Monotype object" are stain, colour, symmetry. Materials such as thick multicoloured paper, brushes, gouache, or watercolour are used. The method of obtaining an image: the child folds a sheet of paper in half and draws an image of an object on one half of it, objects that are symmetrical are chosen. After drawing, before the paint has dried, the sheet is folded in half again to obtain a print. The image can also be decorated, then the letter is also drawn after drawing several elements.

In the techniques of "Ordinary blotography, with a tube, with a thread", the expressive means is a stain. The materials for these techniques are similar: paper, ink or thinly diluted gouache in a bowl, a plastic spoon, a tube (straw for drinks), a thread of medium thickness. The method of obtaining an image using the technique of "Ordinary blotography": the child scoops up the gouache with a plastic spoon and pours it onto the paper. As a result, spots appear in random order. Then the sheet is covered with another sheet and pressed (you can fold the original sheet in half, drip ink on one half, and cover it with the other). Next, the top sheet is removed, the image is examined: it is determined what it looks like. Missing details are drawn [14].

The method of obtaining an image using the technique "Blotography with a tube": the child scoops up paint with a plastic spoon, pours it onto the sheet, making a small spot (droplet). Then blow on this spot from the tube so that its end does not touch either the spot or the paper. If necessary, the procedure is repeated. Missing details are drawn. The method of obtaining an image using the technique "Blotography with a thread": an older preschool child lowers the thread into the paint, wrings it out. Then, on a sheet of paper, he lays out the image from the thread, leaving one end of it free. After that, he puts another sheet on top, presses it, holding it with his hand and pulls the thread by the tip. Missing details are drawn.

The "Splash" technique uses such means of expressiveness as a point, texture. The necessary materials for this: paper, gouache, a hard brush, a piece of thick cardboard or plastic (5.5 cm). The way to get the image: the child puts paint on the brush and hits the cardboard with the brush, which is held above the paper. The paint is splattered on the paper.

Means of expressiveness in the "Leaf Prints" technique are: texture, colour. Materials used for this: paper, leaves of various trees, preferably from the ground, gouache, brushes. The method of obtaining the image: a child of older preschool age covers a leaf of a tree with paints of different colours, then applies it to the paper with one side to obtain a print. Each time, a new sheet is taken for impressions. The stem of the leaf can be finished with a brush.

The technique "Watercolour chalk" uses such means of expression as spot, colour, line. The necessary materials are thick paper, watercolour paints, a sponge, and water in a saucer [10]. The method of obtaining the image: the child wets the paper with water using a sponge, then draws on it with chalk. You can use the

methods of drawing with the end of the palm and the whole palm. When drying, the paper becomes wet again.

According to the technique of "Poking" we described above. Let's note that the means of expression: there is texture, volume. Materials needed: squares of coloured double-sided paper (2·2 cm), magazine and newsprint (for example, for hedgehog needles), pencil, PVA glue in a bowl, thick paper or coloured cardboard for the base.

From the age of six, children can switch to the "landscape monotype" technique. With this technique, the means of expression are: spot, tone, vertical symmetry, image of space in the composition. You can use the following materials: paper, brushes, gouache or watercolour, wet sponge, tiles. The method of obtaining the image: the child folds the letter in half. On one half of the sheet a landscape is drawn, on the other it is reflected in a lake, a river (imprint). The landscape is executed quickly so that the paints do not have time to dry. The half of the sheet intended for printing is wiped with a damp sponge. The original drawing, after a print is made of it, is enlivened with paints to make it more distinct from the print. For monotype, you can also use a sheet of paper and a tile. A drawing is applied to the latter, then it is covered with a wet sheet of paper. The landscape is blurred.

When working with non-traditional techniques, it is good to use children's literature, musical accompaniment, folklore and game material. Such didactic materials help to strengthen the imagination during drawing, contribute to artistic conception and the development of artistic abilities.

Conclusions. Summarizing our research, we note that the concept of "creativity" was defined as a certain characteristic of an individual, which indicates his ability to be creative. It was found that the main criteria for the manifestation of creativity of older preschool children are: the originality of children's performance of creative tasks; using images of some objects to build details of others. It has been proven that the development of creativity of older preschool children is the individual characteristics and qualities of an individual that determine the success of performing a variety of creative activities. Furthermore, it was determined that the development of creativity of older preschool children has several stages: from the superficial, purely external grasp of outlines and qualities to the achievement of the essence and depth of artistic content

The peculiarities of using non-traditional drawing techniques for the development of creativity of older preschool children are considered. It has been proven that visual, motor, and muscular analysers are included in the work when drawing. In addition, drawing develops the intellectual abilities of older preschool children, memory, attention, fine motor skills, teaches the child to think and analyse, compare, generalize, compose and imagine. It was determined that drawing with the use of non-traditional image techniques does not tire children of older preschool age, they maintain high activity and work capacity throughout the time allotted for the task. Non-traditional techniques make it possible to imple-

ment an individual approach to children of older preschool age, to take into account their wishes and interests. Their use contributes to: intellectual development; development of self-confidence; development of spatial thinking; free expression of ideas; development of fine motor skills; freedom of choice of materials and techniques. Also, optimal non-traditional drawing techniques for each age of preschoolers are briefly characterized. It has been determined that for older preschool children, it is most appropriate to work with such techniques as "Stencil printing", "Subject monotype", "Ordinary blotography", "Blotography with a tube", "Blotography with thread", "Spraying", "Leaf impressions", "Watercolour chalk", "Stick".

The authors came to the conclusion that non-traditional art techniques can be used in working with children from the age of two. However, more such techniques are better to start from the age of five and further improve to the primary school period.

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